

BIOLOGY TEACHERS' AFFECTIVE VARIABLES AS PREDICTORS OF JOB PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA: A PATH ANALYTICAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: Biology as a natural science is important for inculcating in students the skills for management of natural resources, provision of good health facilities for the people, supply of adequate food and favourable environment. Despite the importance of Biology to students' academic social and economic developments, students' achievements in Biology at the Senior School Certificate Examinations as conducted by both the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO) are still not satisfactory as indicated by chief examiners' reports of the examination bodies. Research studies as well have been focused on students, teacher, home, school, and environmental factors that can improve students' achievement in school subjects. However, most of the studies in this direction investigated these teacher factors as they influence or predict students' achievement. Only a handful of studies especially in the African climate have studied factors that could influence teachers' job performance. Among the few studies the dominant approach has been the correlation of one or two variables with teachers' job performance, and these studies are scarce in the field of Biology. There is therefore need for more

research attention to be drawn to teachers' job performance, using several variables and methods that can provide causal linkages among the variables.

This study adopted a correlation survey research design. The targeted population comprised all Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State and the sample comprises five hundred Biology teachers, which was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. The instruments used are Teachers Job Performance Scale ($r= 0.859$), Emotional Intelligence Scale ($r= 0.867$), Stress Management Questionnaire ($r= 0.786$), Teachers' Social Ability Scale ($r= 0.625$), The Teaching Anxiety Scale II, Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale ($r= 0.606$), Teacher Self-motivation Scale ($r= 0.632$), and Teacher Expectations Inventory ($r= 0.654$). Data analysis was carried using Path Analysis on AMOS software to answer the research questions

The result shows that the empirical data fits the hypothesized model showing the causal linkages among seven teacher factors and job performance. Job performance has a positive and non-significant relationship with Anxiety and Self-motivation; negative and non-significant relationship with emotional intelligence, Self-Efficacy and Expectation. However, job performance has a negative and significant with Stress Management and Social Ability.

Recommendations were made to highlight the role of Government, Authorities of secondary schools and other stakeholders in ensuring that teachers perform at the highest level to improve the quality of education.

Keywords: *Job performance, Teachers' affective factors, Path analysis*

INTRODUCTION

A good number of school subjects were designed in order to prepare senior secondary school students for economic and social viability. Also, to prepare them for societal responsibilities after passing through secondary school education programmes. Among the senior secondary school subjects that focus at equipping students with basic skills of life and prepare them for further career in education and future outings include Biology. Biology as a natural science is important for inculcating in students the skills for managing natural resources, good health facilities, supplying adequate food. It is likewise a necessity for future learning of

various science-related occupations such as medicine, nursing, pharmacy etc. (John, et. al., 2018). As stated in the National Policy on Education (2008), the main objective of teaching Biology includes building upon the knowledge acquired in JSS level Integrated Science (ITS); understanding of the structure and function of living organism as well as appreciation of nature; acquisition of adequate laboratory and field skills in order to carry out and evaluate experiments and projects in Biology; acquisition of necessary scientific skills for example: observing, classifying and interpreting biological data; relevant knowledge in Biology, needed for future advanced studies in biological science; acquisition of necessary scientific attitudes for problems solving; ability to apply biological principles in everyday life in matters that affects personal, social, environment, community health and economic problems.

Biology as a school subject has a lot of significant roles to play in human life and as such, must be taken very seriously. Several studies (Ango, 2002; Oyedokun, 2002; Nwagbo, 2008; Thomas, 2013; Ogunshola, 2016; Rancas & Maskawa, 2018) identified some variables that contributes to students' achievement in Biology, such as teachers' methods of teaching, students learning styles, classroom variables, school variables, and others that were linked to student achievement in biology in Schools and public examinations. Looking at the crucial role of Biology education, individuals, organizations, stakeholders and Government have introduced several innovations into the teaching and learning of Biology for better students learning outcomes.

Despite various contributions at different levels of education for better outcomes, it has been discovered that students' performance in Biology, especially in public examinations (West African Examination Council [WAEC]) is not encouraging (WAEC Chief Examiners' Report of 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, & 2018). Arising from this report, the need for urgent interventions, and research studies in order to salvage the situation for the better direct and indirect improvement in students' achievement in Biology is inevitable. Directing research attention to factors that influence teachers' job performance may have promise of significantly improving students' achievement in long run, since teachers' job performance has been found by previous research studies to influence students' achievement in school subjects. Mount & Goff (2000) conceived job performance to be among the extremely relevant

concepts in organizational practice. Motowildo (2003) defined job performance as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a given period of time. It means job performance refers to the whole performance of an employee involved at a work place (Jex, 2002). Job performance is the capacity of employee to deliver work related goals and meet up with laid down standard expectations (Hassan, et. al., 2010).

Conclusively, job performance can be understood as the execution or the extent of the execution of the roles of an employee at the workplace. In the context of classroom teaching and learning, Duze (2012) noted that the variables which are indicative of teacher's job performance are good teaching, preparation of lesson note, proper usage of scheme of work, good supervision, classroom management, time management, interpersonal skills (listening, optimism, perceived observation skills and empathy) among others. Afuwape (2017) emphasized that the teachers welfare and disposition to duty in a school as an organizational weapon of productivity. Therefore, job performance of teachers can be measured from multiple sources as submitted by Hanif, (2010) that good teachers do not only deploy their teaching powers to satisfy the class, they also need to be good time managers, efficiently carrying along other duties assigned to them different from teaching. This may include discipline in class, motivating students and maintaining a proper link with the students' parents and school administration among others. Job performance of an individual depends on the support and resources made available by other members of the work environment (Seibert, et al 2001). Arising from research studies, such factors include emotional intelligence (Ahmed, et. al., 2016; Sambu, 2019); Job stress (Blix, et. al., 1994; Koslowsy, 1998; Wilson, 2002; Kyriacou, et. al., 2004); Job anxiety (Aslrasouli & Vahid, 2014; Anusiem & Okoiye, 2015; Egaga, et. al., 2015); Motivation (Nwosu, 2015; Gewasari, et. al., 2017); and social skills (Tapia-Gutierrez, & Cubo-Delgado, 2015; Ukala, 2019) among others.

Emotional Intelligence (EI) is currently a popular concept in nearly all spheres of human endeavour according to Ahmed, et. al. (2016), majorly the relationship between EI and employee's efficiency and performance is being extensively explored. Emotional intelligence has been severally defined, but the definition of Mayer and Salovey (1997) is still considered in the literature as the most widely

acceptable definition. According to Mayer and Salovey (1997), emotional intelligence is the capacity to see feelings, incorporate feelings to work with thought, figure out feelings, and convert these feelings to personal growth. Emotional Intelligence has been shown to be an indispensable factor in determining success in life. Also, EI has been linked to several organizational areas, such as choosing employees, team, etc. (Wall, 2008). In general, emotions are regarded as important concept for teachers' career related discussions (Reio, 2005). Teaching is often seen to be quite stressful (Johnson, et al 2005), involves many challenges as teachers have to deal with high level of emotional exhaustion and burnout (Chang, 2009). Teachers, in executing their jobs should also recognise that both students' emotion and their emotions need regulation (Greenberg, et al 2003). Therefore, EI is a necessity for teachers to control their wellbeing and the socio-emotional development of their students (Sutton, et al 2003).

Goleman (2001) suggested that EI can be understood from its components which include: Self-awareness, self-regulation, social emotional awareness, and relationship awareness. Grayson (2013) characterizes self-awareness as the as the ability to see one's opinions, to isolate between them, to appreciate what one is feeling and why, and to perceive what caused the feelings. Emotional management or self-regulation or self-management is the capacity to resist the urge to panic during provocative or struggling circumstance, while keeping calm and eventually revamping rationality (Wolmarans & Martins, 2001). The relevance of teachers' EI in enhancing performance has initiated increase in research studies (Collie et al, 2012; Corcoran & Tormey, 2012). It is important to note that, a teacher in addition to content knowledge and instructional skills (Hosotani, et. al., 2011) need to possess the ability to communicate his knowledge to the students effectively (Tahir, et. al., 2013). Extensive research (Iupton, et al, 1998; Abraham, 1999; Wong & Law, 2002; Carmelli, 2003; Higgs, 2004; Goleman, 2006) has discovered that EI ensures effective job performance of individuals. O'boyle et al, (2011) exerted that general argument has it that employees with high levels of EI are likely to perform better. Emotional Intelligence contributes positively toward the teaching role (Corcoran & Tormey, 2012), and teachers with high EI seem to be better in recognizing and

regulating their negative emotions and facilitate effective learning environment in classrooms (Krementizer & Miller, 2008).

Another important concept is stress management, a crucial and prominent theme in job performance studies. Stress is common to human daily activities and unavoidable features of our daily lives. It has also become a costlier problem of global concern as it is affecting development of humanity. Hans Selye (1957) defined stress as a general adaptive syndrome or non-specific response to demands placed upon the human body. These demands could either stimulate or threatens the individuals. Erkutlu and chafra (2006) defined stress “as the reaction of individuals to demands imposed upon them”. Teaching could also be associated with high levels of stress (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2008) and teachers’ work stress is an indication of unpleasant emotions as a result of teaching work (Kyriacou, 2001). Such teachers’ work stress do not only come from the demands of administrators, colleagues, students, and parents but also comes from work overload, student misbehaviour, level of conflict with students and colleagues, and a lack of recognition for accomplishments among several others (Greenglass & Burke, 2003). Research studies (Boyle et al, 1995; Betoret, 2006; Jepson & Forrest, 2006; Kyriacou, 2010; McCarthy, et. al., 2009; Klassen & Chiu, 2011) show that teachers’ work stress, despite the cause has been associated with several negative outcomes such as increased burnout, reduced sense of teaching efficacy, lower self-efficacy, reduced job satisfaction, poorer teacher-student relationship, and lower levels of effectiveness.

Considering the stressful nature of the teaching profession, as identified in the foregoing discussion, and its grave consequences on the teacher and the entire educational system, then the need to focus attention on strategies individuals adopt to handle and reduce the effects of the perceived and experienced stress (stress management) strategies by teachers become inevitable. Randlhawa (2009) examined the three aspects of stress management studies to include: to identity the various sources of teacher stress and its negative consequences; to identity various coping strategies as adopted by teachers and, what should be the right methodology in the measurement of teacher stress for researchers in future. Bernstein, et. al., (2003), Gazzaniga and Heatherton (2006) discussed the strategies for coping with stress can be cognitive, emotional, behavioural, or physical. Specific methods suggested by

other researchers which could be classified under these broad categories include; counselling (Hayes, 2001), relaxation technique such as visualization and biofeedback (Anspaugh, et. al., 2003), assertiveness (Duffy, 1999), diet (Addison & Yankyera, 2015), meditation (Hales 2001). Although most studies concentrate on the impact of stress and stress levels on such variables as job satisfaction, effectiveness and performance of teachers, few studies have shown that there could also exist linkages among teachers preferred or dominant stress management technique and their job satisfaction, effectiveness, and performance as well as their students' achievements (Addison, & Yankyera, 2015).

One other factor that could be linked to, or even serve as an indicator (Mohamad, & Jais, 2016) of teachers EI as well as stress management is social skills or social ability or Interpersonal skills. Since humans are social beings who live through a series of interactions across different phases and spheres of coexistence. That is, from infancy to adulthood, within varying contexts, such as the family, friends, and professional circles. Teachers, more than other professionals, are expected to be conversant with what is required to set up these relationships in a manner that will bring about harmony, so as to bring about an appropriate climate for teaching and learning (Caballo, 2007). Coronado (2009) defined social skills as an array of abilities harnessed to produce effective behaviours in interpersonal situations aimed at getting satisfactory behavioural responses from others. That is, individual's capability in managing relationship with others. According to Garcia (2009) social skills involve the ability to interact with others in a given social context, in a stipulated manner, well accepted or valued socially, and being also beneficial to others. This array of skills that are termed social skills includes; respect for others, mutual regard, commitment, openness, tolerance, empathy, negotiation, communication etc. (Schuetz, 2011). It can be stated that the general objective of social skills lies on providing the individual with the tools to be able to face social and situational interactions he is presented with in a satisfactory fashion. Social skills have been measured in the literature using a wide range of indicators depending on the facet of the concept considered by different researchers. According to Manrique, (2016), the indicators of social skills in teachers could include: Assertive Communication, leadership, conflict Resolution, and Planning.

Social skills are very important for the teaching profession (Tapia-Gutierrez & Cubo-Delgado, 2015). They have been reported to have an impact on learning, interpersonal relations, coexistence, mental health and the collaboration of students and teachers as well as in teacher's effectiveness (Becerra, 2009; Fernandez et al. 2009; Goleman, 2006; Imbernon, 2006; Mourshed, 2008; Naranjo, 2007; Tapia-Gutierrez & Cubo-Delgado, 2015). Social skills are also commonly found to have significant relationship between conscientiousness and work performance, and social skill also found to moderate the association among mental health, job performance and pay (Ferris, et al 2001). Therefore, attempt to improve teachers job performance, with the ultimate aim of improving students' learning outcomes should likely not only focus on the academic competencies of a teacher, but also take into consideration, the social abilities of the teacher.

Motivation is another variable that has been demonstrated to have significant weight on the outcomes of employees, as well as the life of an organization. The behaviour of employees in a work environment can be moderated through motivation, and from situation to situation, the level of motivation differs among people (Robbins et al, 2005). Teachers' motivation is quite vital, since it could influence (Mustafa & Othman, 2010). Motivation guides people's actions and behaviour toward achievement of some goals (Analoui, 2000). Motivation could be intrinsic or extrinsic in nature (Sansone & Harackiewicz, 2000). As a result of the stressful nature of the teaching profession as discussed, teachers are often times poorly motivated by their work environment and conditions. Adelabu (2005) found in Nigeria that teacher's motivation is very poor and teachers are also dissatisfied with their working environment and salary conditions. The various stressors in the teaching profession including: low income as compared to other professionals, poor work environment, no decision making authority, and little opportunities for self-development among others have been identified as the major causes of teachers' poor (extrinsic) motivation. Self-motivation has been conceived as doing what needs to be done without prompting, supervision, influence, or push from others (Self-Motivation Techniques & Examples, 2018). Motivation has been linked with several other variables in the teaching and learning industry. Dai and Stenberg (2004) revealed that high levels of job dissatisfaction, stress can influence motivation and job

performance negatively. Michaelowa (2002) in her study on analysis of the key determinants of teacher's motivation in the developing country context, found that large class size, double-shifting, rural location, high educational attainment and active parental involvement negatively correlated with teacher job satisfaction in Nigeria. The development of motivation strategies has an important role in motivating workforce to deliver high levels of performance, discretionary effort and contribution (Nwosu, 2015).

It would also be significant to think that beyond motives, a person's perceived capability to accomplish a certain level of performance would have influence on the actual performance. Several concepts have been built around such perceived ability. Self-efficacy; which is one of such concepts, is a feeling of satisfaction that one has in himself or herself, or confidence (the second concept) and satisfaction in oneself, and self-respect (www.merriam-webster.com). Self-esteem, another concept, has been conceived by Lawrence (2006) as "the individual's evaluation of discrepancy between self-image and ideal self". These three concepts have been used by different commentators sometimes to mean the same things and by others differently. Bandura (1977) sees "self-efficacy" as the belief one has in being able to execute a specific task successfully (e.g., solving a math problem) in order to obtain a certain outcome (e.g., self-satisfaction or teacher recognition) and, thus, can be considered as situational specific self-confidence. Bandura (1986) also noted that self-efficacy is not concerned with an individual's skills, but, rather, with the judgments of what an individual can accomplish with those skills. As seen in his submissions, Bandura viewed the concepts to be different from one another. Bandura (1986, 1990) distinguishes between "self-efficacy" and "self-confidence" by explaining that self-confidence refers to firmness or strength of belief but does not specify its direction; while self-efficacy implies that a goal has been set. The US National Research Council, (1994) rejected Bandura's distinction, and adopted the term "self-confidence" for self-efficacy, because it is more familiar to most individuals.

Self-confidence is one of the most influential motivators and regulators of behaviour in people's everyday lives (Bandura, 1986), Although the bulk of previous research investigating self-esteem and self-confidence (self-efficacy) have been focused on the learners (Earley & Lituchy, 1991; Hackett, 1985; Ozer & Bandura, 1990, Schunk,

1981 Wood & Bandura, 1989), a few studies (Bandura, 1986; Feltz & Mugno, 1983, 1988) have researched teachers' self-confidence, and how it may be linked to other variables such as their self-motivation, job satisfaction and performance. In general, these studies have found self-confidence to be a major determinant of performance. In the present study, self-confidence will be considered as a dimension of self-esteem and synonymous with self-efficacy, and will be conceived as the belief that one can successfully execute a specific activity, rather than a global trait that accounts for overall performance optimism. For example, one may have a lot of self-confidence in one's ability at golf but very little self-confidence in one's tennis skills. It has been established in the foregoing that the teachers' job is associated with high levels of stress, which makes it imperative for the teacher to be highly self-motivated and self-confident to be able to manage the stress theoretically.

Asides from being stressful, teaching have been widely identified as a profession that is full of anxiety (Kaplan in Aslrasouli & Vahid, 2014). Anxiety perceived by teachers in different situations can be defined as a complex psychological phenomenon influenced by a myriad of variables. For instance, during teaching in classroom, some teachers could be nervous, apprehensive and frightened, not necessarily due to intellectual incompetence but anxiety. It is an experience which if not well managed, could make teachers to express poor teaching efficacy. Describing the nature of teaching anxiety, Gardner and Leak in Anusiem and Okoiye, (2015) proposed that teaching anxiety is a state condition and not a personality characteristic, but an association the individual had made between anxiousness and teaching. This condition is probably linked with years of teaching experience, and is mostly observed among newly employed teachers, as Akinsola, (2008) noted that anxiety for teaching is a frequent fear of pre-service teachers which can lead to series of task avoidance. Teaching anxiety according to Aslrasouli and Vahid (2014) can be adequately viewed as one demanding concepts among teachers; teaching anxiety has been found to reflect real or perceived knowledge deficits in subject content as well as in skill of delivery. Akinsola (2002) found out that elementary in-service mathematics teachers' anxiety affects their studying and teaching of mathematics negatively and also have a debilitating effect on their problem-solving ability. This may be due to perceive knowledge deficits in mathematics content as well as in

mathematics teaching skills, and memories of past occurrences of mathematics failure or mathematics anxiety (Levine, 1993). Whatever the cause of anxiety, amounts of anxiety can differ from an individual to the other based on variables such as gender, experience, marital status, age, and the type of organization one is engaged with (Aslrasouli & Vahid, 2014). Studies by Daniel, (2011); Ameen, et. al., (2010) among others have involved the measurement of anxiety among different categorizations of individuals, and linking anxiety with several other variables including age, gender, experience, position. It might be as well reasonable to research the possible linkages among anxiety and other variables in attempt to explain teachers' job performance, which is the aim of the study.

Teachers' expectation is another variable that can be considered as having potential influence on teachers' job performance. In the literature, teachers' expectation is often used to refer to teachers' expectation of students' attributes and achievement. In the international context, researchers have been interested in teacher expectations as a possible mechanism through which the achievement gap between majority and minority students, boys and girls, and students from more or less affluent families could emerge and grow (e.g., Jussim et al. 1996; McKown & Weinstein 2008; Riley & Ungerleider 2012; Glock & Krolak- Schwerdt 2013; Sorhagen 2013). Teacher expectations have been linked in previous studies, mostly to teachers' experience. In this view, multiple studies have demonstrated that a disconnection exists between the expectations of pre-service teachers and the reality of the teaching profession (Cole & Knowles, 1993; Hebert, 2002; Chase, 2006; DiCiccio, et. al., 2014). However, in the present study, DeRosa (2016) concept of teacher expectations will be adopted, in which teacher expectations will refer to classroom teachers expectation in terms of personal expectations, expectations of teaching responsibilities, expectations of administration, expectations of professional support, and expectations of the classroom environment. The focus is to investigate how teacher expectations measured from these dimensions will influence teachers' job performance among other variables, which is undoubtedly a rather rare research direction.

The persistent unsatisfactory achievement of students in Biology at senior secondary school level as discussed earlier calls for more research focusing on multiple factors that can potentially influence or improve students' achievement. Since the teacher

has been identified as a singular individual contributing greatly to the learning of students, such research efforts should take particular interest in teachers' job performance, which eventually leads to students' improved ability. This definite call prompted the researcher to investigate the extent to which teacher factors (Emotional intelligence, Stress management, Social ability, Teacher anxiety, Self-confidence, Self-motivation & Teacher expectations) can predict the job performance of Biology teachers in Lagos State, using a path analytical model.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigated the causal linkages among seven teacher factors (Emotional intelligence, Stress management, Social skills, Teacher anxiety, Self-confidence, Self-motivation, Teacher expectations) and Biology teachers' job performance in Lagos state.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

This research adopted correlation survey research design. This study fits the correlation survey design which involves determining the existing causal relationships between two or more variables.

Population:

Eight hundred (800) Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State of Nigeria were regarded and involved as the target population of the study.

Sample and sampling technique:

The study sample comprises three hundred and fifty (350) Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State, which was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure.

Research Instruments:

Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS): This scale was adapted from the TJPS developed by Hanif and Pervez (2004). TJPS comprised of 25 items with four-point rating scale ("Never", "Sometimes", "Very Often" & "Always"), with four sub-scale

categories of teacher's job performance such as teaching skills, management skills, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal skills.

Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS): It was adapted from EI (Pc Sc) scale by Mehta & Singh, (2013) following 13 out of the 18 competences of the Emotional and Social Competency Inventory (ESCI). EIS is a 4-point Likert-type scale (“Never “Sometimes”, “Very Often” & “Always”).

Stress Management Questionnaire (SMQ): SMQ is also a self-report instrument adapted from the 14-item Female Teachers Coping or managing stress questionnaire by Cooper & Cartwright (1997). SMQ contains 25 items designed to measure coping strategies on a 4-point scale ranging from Never to Always.

Teachers' Social Ability Scale (TSAS): TSAS is a four likert scale instrument adopted based on five relationships of management competences (Influence, Coach & mentor, Inspirational leadership, Teamwork and Conflict Management). The instrument has four response options such as “Never “Sometimes”, “Very Often and “Always”.

Teaching Anxiety Scale II (TCHAS2): TCHAS developed by Parsons, (1973) was adopted in the study. It contains 25 items eliciting information on anxiety of teachers.

Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale (TSES): TSES is a self-report instrument, adopted from Bandura self-efficacy instrument. It is a 30-item instrument with 7 subscales such as decision making efficacy, school resources efficacy, instructional efficacy, disciplinary efficacy, parental involvement efficacy, efficacy to enlist community involvement efficacy, and positive school climate efficacy (Bandura, 1997).

Teacher Self-motivation Scale (TSMS): TSMS is a four point likert scale instrument which was adapted from the personal attributes of emotional intelligence presented in Serrat's Model (Serrat, 2009). The instrument has four subscales based on the personal competences that define self-motivation (Achievement drive, Commitment, Initiative, Optimism).

Teacher expectations Inventory (TEI): TEI is a 30 items questionnaire with four response options ranging from Never, to Sometimes, Very Often and Always. The

instrument has five subscales (teaching responsibilities, administration, professional support, students' outcomes and classroom/teaching environment).

Validation of instrument

The validity (adequacy & contents validity) of Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS), Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS), Stress Management Questionnaire (SMQ), Teachers' Social Ability Scale (TSAS), The Teaching Anxiety Scale II (TCHAS2), Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale (TSES), Teacher Self-motivation Scale (TSMS), and the Teacher Expectations Inventory (TEI) were determined by ensuring that all the instruments were checked by experts to ensure contents and face validity. Their corrections, opinions, and recommendations were used to modify the instrument.

Furthermore, the instruments were administered on 40 Biology teachers outside the sample but within the study population. Cronbach's alpha statistic was computed for the instruments using data or responses obtained from the 40 teachers. The reliability coefficients of the instruments are TJPS = 0.859, EIS = 0.867, SMQ = 0.786, TSAS = 0.625, TCHAS2 = 0.802, TSES = 0.606, TSMS = 0.632, TEI = 0.654.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Research Question one: What is the most meaningful causal model showing how the seven independent variables predict Biology teachers' job performance in Lagos state?

Figure 4.2: The re-specified hypothesized model or causal linkages among the variables.

Key: X_1 = expectation, X_2 = anxiety, X_3 = self-efficacy, X_4 = self-motivation, X_5 = social ability, X_6 = Stress management, X_7 = Emotional intelligence and Y_2 = Job Performance

The outcome showed that the Chi-square (χ^2) fit index ($\chi^2= 18.635$, $p= 0.179$) provides an estimated index that shows the data provides a good fit to the hypothesized model (figure 4.2) because the chi-square probability exceeds the recommended criterion (i.e., $p > 0.05$; according to Hair et al., 2006; Bayram, 2013). Secondly, Comparative Fit Index (CFI= 0.990) provides an estimated index that show the data provides a good fit to the hypothesized model (Figure 4.2). By comparing this Comparative Fit Index with the saturated model, it exceeds the recommended criterion (i.e., $CFI > 0.95$; according to Schumacker & Lomax, 2004 & Bayram, 2013). Also, Normed Fit Index (NFI) index (NFI = 0.962) shows that the data analysed fits the hypothesized model because the NFI exceeds the recommended criterion (i.e., $NFI > 0.90$; according to Bayram, 2013). The RMSEA index (0.031) provides an estimated index that shows the data provides a good fit to the hypothesized model (figure 4.2). This is because the index exceeds the recommended criterion (i.e., $RMSEA < 0.07$; Hair et al., 2006 & Bayram, 2013). Finally, Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.980) provides an index that shows the data provides a good fit to the hypothesized model (figure 4.2) because the TLI index exceed the recommended criterion (i.e., $TLI > 0.95$; according to Schumacker & Lomax, 2004; Bayram, 2013).

Overall, all the five model fit indices such as Chi-square (χ^2), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) indicates that the data collected fits the hypothesized model.

Research Question two:

Which of the contributions from the seven teachers' factors to the prediction of teachers' job performance are through direct and indirect effects?

Table 4.1: Summary of contributions through direct, indirect and total causal effects

Outcome	Determinants	Causal effects		
		Direct	Indirect	Total
Self-efficacy	Expectation	0.374	-	0.374
Self-motivation	Expectations	0.189	-	0.189
	Anxiety	0.403	-	0.403
Social ability	Expectations	0.172	0.186	0.358
	Self-efficacy	0.496	-	0.496
Stress Management	Expectations	0.103	0.121	0.224
	Anxiety	0.366	0.082	0.447
	Self-efficacy	-	0.115	0.115
	Self-motivation	0.203	-	0.203
	Social ability	0.231	-	0.231
Emotional Intelligence	Expectations	0.107	0.148	0.254
	Self-efficacy	-	0.204	0.204
	Social ability	0.412	-	0.412
Job Performance	Expectations	-	-0.026	-0.026
	Anxiety	0.111	-0.051	0.060
	Self-efficacy	-	-0.013	-0.013
	Self-motivation	-	-0.023	-0.023
	Social ability	-	-0.027	-0.027
	Stress management	-0.115	-	-0.115

Table 4.1 presents the contributions from the seven teachers' factors to the prediction of teachers' job performance through direct and indirect effects. From the table, self-efficacy had Expectation as its predictor in the model which only had direct and total effects on self-efficacy. Expectation had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.374 on self-efficacy. This means that when Expectation increases by 1 standard deviation, self-efficacy increases by 0.374 standard deviation. Furthermore, expectations revealed a total effect of 0.374 on self-efficacy. This means as Expectation increases by 1 standard deviation, self-efficacy increases by 0.374 standard deviation.

Self-motivation in the model had predictors such as Expectations and anxiety. For direct effects, Expectation had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.189 and anxiety had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.403 on self-motivation respectively. This means that as Expectation and anxiety increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.189 and 0.403 in the standard deviation value of self-motivation respectively. Also, Expectations had a total effect value of 0.189 and Anxiety had a total effect value of 0.403 on self-motivation respectively. This means as expectation and anxiety and self-efficacy increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.189 and 0.403 in the standard deviation value of self-motivation respectively.

Focusing on social ability, it has several predictors such as expectations and self-efficacy. On the direct effects, expectation had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.172, and self-efficacy had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.496 respectively. It means that as expectation and self-efficacy increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.172 and 0.496 in the standard deviation value of social ability respectively. For indirect effects, expectation had an indirect (mediated) effect value of 0.186. It means when expectation increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.186 in the standard deviation value of social ability through another variable. Finally, expectation had a total effect value of 0.358 and self-efficacy had a total effect value of 0.496 on social ability respectively. This means that as expectation and self-efficacy increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.358 and 0.496 respectively in the standard deviation value of social ability.

For stress management as criterion and endogenous variable in the model, it has several predictors such as expectations, anxiety, self-efficacy, self-motivation and social ability. Focusing on direct effects, expectation had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.103, Anxiety had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.366, Self-Motivation had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.203 and Social Ability had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.231 on stress management. Therefore, it means as expectations, anxiety, self-motivation and social ability increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.103, 0.366, 0.203 and 0.231

respectively in the standard deviation value of stress management. On the indirect effects, expectations had an indirect (mediated) effect value of 0.121, anxiety had an indirect (mediated) effect value of 0.082 and self-efficacy had an indirect (mediated) effect value of 0.115 on stress management respectively through other variables. It means as expectations, anxiety and self-efficacy increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.121, 0.082, and 0.115 respectively in the standard deviation value of stress management through other variables. Finally, expectations had a total effect value of 0.224, anxiety had a total effect value of 0.447, self-efficacy had a total effect value of 0.115, self-motivation had a total effect value of 0.203 and social ability had a total effect value of 0.231 on stress management respectively. This means that when expectations, anxiety, self-efficacy, self-motivation and social ability increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increment of 0.224, 0.447, 0.115, 0.203 and 0.231 respectively in the standard deviation value of stress management.

On the fifth endogenous variable which is emotional Intelligence, it has several predictors such as expectations, self-efficacy and social ability. On direct effects, expectations had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.107 and social ability had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.412 on emotional intelligence. This means that if the standard deviation of expectations and social ability increases by 1, there will be a corresponding increase of 0.107 and 0.412 respectively in the standard deviation value of emotional Intelligence. Looking into indirect effects, expectations had an indirect (mediated) effect value of 0.148 and Self-Efficacy had an indirect (mediated) effect value of 0.204 on emotional intelligence through other variables. This means when expectations and self-efficacy increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.148 and 0.204 respectively in the standard deviation value of emotional Intelligence through other variables. Finally, the total effects show that Expectations had a total effect value of 0.254, Self-Efficacy had a total effect value of 0.204 and Social Ability had a total effect value of 0.412 on emotional intelligence. This means that as Expectations, Self-Efficacy and Social Ability increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.254, 0.204 and 0.412 respectively in the standard deviation value of emotional Intelligence.

Finally, on the last endogenous variable which is Job Performance, it has several predictors such as expectations, anxiety, self-efficacy, self-motivation, social ability and Stress Management. For direct effect, anxiety had a direct (unmediated) effect value of 0.111 and stress management had a direct (unmediated) effect value of -0.115 on Job Performance. It means that as Anxiety increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.111 in the standard deviation value of Job Performance. However, as stress management increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding decrease of 0.115 in the standard deviation value of Job Performance. Also, on indirect effects, Expectations had an indirect (mediated) effect value of -0.026, Anxiety had an indirect (mediated) effect value of -0.051, Self-Efficacy had an indirect (mediated) effect value of -0.013, Self-Motivation had an indirect (mediated) effect value of -0.023, and social ability had an indirect (mediated) effect value of -0.027 on Job Performance through other variables. It means that as Expectations, Anxiety, Self-Efficacy, Self-Motivation and Social ability had an indirect (mediated) increase by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding decrease of 0.026, 0.051, 0.013, 0.023, 0.027 standard deviation value of Job Performance respectively. Considering total effects, expectations had a total effect value of -0.026, anxiety had a total effect value of 0.060, self-efficacy had a total effect value of -0.013, self-motivation had a total effect value of -0.023, social ability had a total effect value of -0.027 and Stress Management had a total effect value of -0.115. This means that as Expectations, Self-Efficacy, Self-Motivation, Social Ability and Stress Management increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding decrease of 0.026, 0.013, 0.023, 0.027 and 0.115 standard deviation values of Job Performance respectively. However, as anxiety increases by 1 standard deviation, there is a corresponding increase of 0.060 standard deviation value of Job Performance.

Discussion

The empirical data fits the hypothesized model showing the causal linkages among seven teacher factors (Emotional intelligence, Stress management, Social skills, Teacher anxiety, Self-confidence, Self-motivation, Teacher expectations) and Biology teachers' job performance. The path model is over-identified and the entire

five models fit indices such as Chi-square (χ^2), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) indicates that the empirical data collected fits the hypothesized model. Having an over-identified model shows that path analysis could be conducted and the corresponding generated data could be interpreted. As the empirical data fits the hypothesized model, it shows that a parsimonious model is generated which could help provide information on the relationship or causal linkages among the exogenous and endogenous variables.

The result revealed that job performance has a non-significant, low but inverse relationship with emotional intelligence, Self-Efficacy and Expectation. Furthermore, job performance has a non-significant, low and direct relationship with Anxiety and Self-motivation. Conversely, job performance has a significant, low but inverse relationship with Stress Management and Social Ability. This finding contradicts the report of Reio (2005), Khosa & Khan (2016) and Goleman, (2006) on the correlation between job performance and emotional intelligence where it shows that positive relationship exists. Furthermore, it contradicts the report of Davis (2009) and Suyato (2009) on the correlation between job performance and self-efficacy because it shows a positive relationship. Furthermore, it contradicts the report of Derosa (2016) and chase (2016) on the correlation between job performance and self-efficacy as it shows positive relationship. It opposes the report of Akinsola (2008) on the relationship between job performance and anxiety due to negative relationship. It supports the report of Nwosu (2015), Mashaqbah (2018) on the correlation between job performance and motivation; supports the report of gravers and Coopos (2003) on the relationship between job performance and stress and support the report of Chukwu (2018), Delgado (2015) on the correlation between job performance and social ability. The connection or relationship between all the predictor variables is very crucial to bringing out the best from the teachers through their performance since teachers are the implementer of the curriculum; manages and control the teaching and learning process in school.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The investigation showing the causal linkages among seven teacher factors (Emotional intelligence, Stress management, social skills, Teacher anxiety, Self-confidence, Self-motivation, Teacher expectations) and Biology teachers' job performance in Lagos state is the aim of the study. The result showed that the empirical data fits the hypothesized model showing the causal linkages among seven teacher factors (Emotional intelligence, Stress management, social skills, teacher anxiety, self-confidence, self-motivation, teacher expectations) and biology teachers' job performance. Furthermore, job performance has non-significant, low but inverse relationship with emotional intelligence, stress management, self-efficacy and expectation. Furthermore, job performance has a non-significant, low and direct relationship with anxiety and self-motivation. Conversely, job performance has a significant, low but inverse relationship with social ability.

Recommendations

1. Government should employ more teachers into the education system to reduce stress and workload of the existing teachers within the school system because teachers' stress management affects job performance negatively
2. Also, Government and principals of secondary schools should find means of bringing either full time and part-time teachers into the schools to reduce teachers' stress and workload to improve or create time for teachers to improve their social ability at work through interactions, socialization and other activities that will improve their teachers' social abilities.
3. Teachers should also be motivated by giving them more incentives and making their work environment comfortable so that it could improve their performance
4. Teachers' Emotional intelligence should be properly managed by teachers and with the aid of seminars on health, stress and emotional management to help teachers balance their emotional with classroom activities and job performance.

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